

Employee Selection- Getting Right People for the Right Job by Using Effective Selection Tool

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Abstract

The challenge for today's Management is to select the right person for the right job who can create and nurture a pool of growth of the Institution. It starts with the selection process of the employees. 'Interview' has been considered as an essential selection method by management for a long time. The cost of rehiring and retraining enhances the expenditure of the Institution, signifying the importance of hiring the right person for the correct position first. It requires a reliable and valid interview process. This study attempts to promote a systematic approach towards selecting the candidate using Google Forms as a useful selection tool. This paper covers employee hiring and selection. It addresses recruitment and selection from the perspective of an institution, especially for the service sector where human labor plays a significant role in the working of the institution. Proper implementation of this method towards hiring will assure the selection of the most beautiful person. The paper is an Empirical Research conducted in the Service sector, i.e., Educational Institution. The research was done using both primary and secondary data. Primary data was obtained from 40 employees by using questionnaire method with the help of Google forms. The research findings expose that best selection process, and they are satisfied with the organizational climate, and the organization follows ethical and fair recruitment policy.

Keywords: Selection, Google Forms.

Introduction

Human resource management is an essential function of an organization. Among the HR practices, recruitment and selection play a vital role where employees entry into the organizations. Recruitment is the process of searching for prospective employees to apply for the job posting in the institution. Selection is the process of choosing a suitable candidate among the job applicants. Many of the researchers say that recruitment and selection policies should be ethical for the organizations to sustain in the competitive environment. Recruitment is the first step, then after selection and placement comes in the employment process (Rao, 2010). Employers aim to choose an appropriate candidate suitable for that particular job.

Selection is the practice of manpower planning. Selection is the process of choosing the appropriate candidate which matches the

candidate skills and the job requirements (Bhattacharyya, 2010). The selection process will be lengthy for large organizations and will be more extensive for manufacturing organizations, and it differs from one industry to others (Venkatesh, 2008). As this a manufacturing organization, its process will be wider in departments and activities. According to Dale, Yoder selection means dividing the total job applicants into two classes as selected and not selected (K. Aswathapa, 2007). The selection process followed at various education institutions is like referral background, Personal Interviews, which includes oral as well as conducting a written test.

Review of Literature

From the human resource management perspective, the first most crucial and difficult social resource management strategy for achieving organizational goals are recruitment and selection strategies, as the outcome of recruitment and selection strategy can be very productive for the organization if selected right person in terms of appropriate skills mix and also very nonproductive if wrong one was selected and can lead failure of the organizations (Compton, 2009 & Canton, 2004).

Effective recruitment and selection have always been one of a most pivotal for the organizations in the educational sector because of not having any absolute methodology for attracting, screening and finally finding the right person for the right job in an organization (Pounder, 1996).

Researchers have been working on the three perspectives that have helped to develop fair selection procedures, and in this regard, ten procedural rules have been suggested to assess the fairness of any selection system (Gilliland 1993).

Cropanzana (2007) conducted research on applicants' reaction to examine the violation of the procedural rules and found that job-relatedness and interpersonal treatment of the selection procedure were more concerned to the applicants while as applicants showed concerns over not receiving timely feedback and biasness.

Applicants perception and reaction to the selection procedures have attached huge interest among different researchers who analyzed it in different perspectives, and among these a dominant focus is the fairness of selection procedures, that has an impact not only on the organizations attractiveness (Bauer et al., 1998) but also on the applicant's motivation regarding a particular selection test (Chan et al., 1997).

It has been argued that fairly treated applicants recommend the organization to others while as in case of not fairly not treated may go for litigation for their possible remedy (Bauer et al., (2001).

Kandola and Zottoli & Wanous, (2000) has identified from the research that informal recruitment (employee referrals and Walk-in) had been considered more helpful to the job applicants because these sources provide accurate and complete set of knowledge about a particular job with some other advantages over the formal recruitment sources (advertisement & Posters). Zoltoli & Wanous, (2000) has found that the advertisements place in the different newspapers has been found least useful source of recruitment in both the public and private sector as well. Fullerton (1994) have argued that to remove the discrimination, the main principle is that process should be made in such a way that applicants will experience sameness in treating them during the whole selection process. Powel, (1991) have explained that there are many researchers who have pointed out about the many recruiters who are providing applicants enough and specific information which enables them to decide about the suitability and relevancy with the job.

Vianen et al., (2004) argued that in making selection of an employee the situational judgment test has a higher rating as compared to the cognitive ability and personality test. It has been argued that by using technology in the field of recruitment and selection has many advantages and this can enhance the level of validity, acceptance and also will be able to bring efficiency in

an organizational recruitment and selection activities (Chan & Schmitt, 1997). Researchers have raised various concerns over the transparency of the selection procedures that according to (Brink, at. Al, 2006) is very critical.

Some researchers argued that women candidates qualify more in open competition as compare to male candidates which (Van Balen, 2001) has found that this is because of the lack of transparency in selection procedures. However, (Brink at. al, 2006) has found that women can have more probability to be appointed if the selection committee consists of a significant number of women members.

According to the Burack (1985) recruitment sources are closely linked to the organizational activities as the performance of employees, employee turnover, employee satisfaction, employee wishes and the commitment of the organization (Burack, 1980). These recruitment and selection process should be done in every sector for fulfilling their organizational goals (Nartey, 2012).

Recruitment and selection practices were essential in the police department as said by Michael D. White, and Glipsy Escobar (2008) in the world and this paper shows the importance of seven issues relating to recruitment, selection and training practices in the organizations (M.N. Malhotra, 2014) (Terpstra.D, 1996). Mohammed Nurul Absar (2012) says the importance of recruitment and selection in his paper by considering both public and private manufacturing firms in Bangladesh (M.M. Absar, 2012).

Some of the research professionals and scholars say that there is a close linkage between the recruitment selection employee satisfaction organization performance and HR practices (Gorter, 1996). In his paper Recruitment and Selection of public workers: An international compendium of modern trends and practices say that the importance of using technology in the recruitment and selection process for updating the organizational resources (Hays, 2004).

Ongori Henry and Temtime Z (2009) say that in their paper, the recruitment and selection practices of the small and medium enterprises and make them improve their HR practices (R.D. Omolo, 2012). French says that the importance of individual selection and recruitment activities in the organizations (G.R. French, 2012). Among recruitment sources Bernardin says

Human resource Personnel and Line management role Researchers have suggested and agreed that human resource policies must be integrated with the overall strategic objectives of the organization, human resource managers and specialists needs exceptional attention to the recruitment and selection of employees to align its consistency with the overall organizational strategy and other subsequent functions of human resource management, this function should be treated as integrated process not taken as casual or an ad hoc activity (Hsu, 2000). The first interaction between an organization and applicant is happening on the recruitment and selection stage when a new candidate perceives fairness treatment from the organization which has long-lasting effects after this candidate joins the organization as an employee (Cropanzana et al., 2007).

Plychart (2006) has noted that the effective selection of an employee is only possible when organizations can generate a larger pool of potential applicants. It has been argued that fairly treated applicants recommend the organization to others while as in case of not fairly not treated may go for litigation for their possible remedy (Bauer et al., 2001). Kandola and Fullerton, (1994) have argued that to remove the discrimination, the main principle is that process should be made in such a way that applicants will experience sameness in treating them during the whole selection process. Gilliland, (1993) suggested that fairness reaction by the applicants may have a relationship with the legal action against the recruiter. Mitsuhashi et al., (1998) has found in the context of Chinese firm's effectiveness of HR practices between the line and HR executive and he noted that Line executive perceive lower HR department performance as compare to them which they argued that are due to the lack of appropriate authority and huge governmental influences in their activities.

Lewis, (2002) has argued that in Chinese State-Owned enterprises the management has not been able to foster proper human resource management practices, which has caused multiple issues for the organizational management like overstaffing and lack of having appropriate expertise required by the organizations. Hsu, (2000) has discussed that the human resource decision making sharing between HR specialist and line managers, he found that line managers have more influence over the human resource specialist in terms of recruitment and selection decision. Tulubas & Celep, (2012) have argued that it is the supervisor who has direct impact on the daily activities of the faculty members as they remain physically and personally very close to these faculty members. Armstrong (1992) has described that the basic job of the human resource specialist is to provide assistance and support to the line managers, which doesn't mean that they control their activities. Organization and state politics Vigoda, (2000) has identified that organizational politics has affected negatively the employee's reaction and has found that in the public sector organizations the employee prefers silence by showing negligent behavior if they feel politics around them, as they don't want to quite the job.

Lee & Renzetti (1990) have declared that researchers who held researches on the recruitment & selection are actually talking a very sensitive area to be analyzed with some ethical & legal consequences, while as according to the (Taylor, 2006) the research investigation in managerial practices which clashes with the prevailing social norms and exposure of asymmetrical power relation can be threatening. Schneider (1992) has argued that the performance of an organization in public sector depends on its managers who are running these organizations and managing its overall affairs, this also depends on those people who have the appointing authority of these managers. In the public institutions it has become common that recruitment and selection practices are facing the issue of unfair practices and in USA & UK nepotism and cronyism is the main acquisition upon these public institutions (Taylor, 2006). Schneider (1992) has mentioned that in 1945 post era Brazil was one of an effective state-led industrialization, but due to severe issues in the bureaucracy and political involvement especially in the field of recruitment and selection, this couldn't be maintained. Taylor, (2006) suggested that the researchers should focus on the political and ethical aspects of the recruitment and selection practices rather than looking into the economic and technical aspects. Krause, (2006) mentioned that citizen elect their members in a democratic set up to work for them but the struggle starts once these members interact with the bureaucracy of the agency or organization to implement their policies and on the other hand the bureaucracy tries to maintain their independence, in such cases the politicians select their non-elected supporters in the public offices that generate multiple agency issues. Suleiman, (2003) has highlighted that in many countries it has been observed that due to political appointees, the organizational performance and morale has been negatively hit, that has caused a hurdle in the way of effective recruitment and selection. Many countries are hiring top position, or executive are being selected with the approval by the top politicians and rest are being selected through organizational internal prevailing mechanism (Krause, 2006) and this sort of system of selection procedures are also prevailing among the most of the SAARC countries including Azad Jammu & Kashmir, Pakistan as well. The struggle of appointing officials in the public sector organizations between the president and other ministers depends on the pressure from their supporters as President has more pressure as compare to the other ministers to appoint near relatives or supporters in the state-owned institutions even they try to do this with the lower-level jobs as well (Schneider, 1992).

Lew, (2007) has explained that it is evident from the literature that political appointments to have more political control hurt the organizational performance and found that due to longer experience in the programs the bureau chief performance was higher than those chiefs who have been politically appointed. Huber & McCarty (2004) has argued that the bureaucrats sometimes may not listen to

the politicians, and in such cases, these politicians will punish them in by all means. Researchers have elucidated that the basic objective of the career merit system was to enhance the capability & capacity of government to perform effectively because of having the relevant knowledge, skills and professional background (Kaufman 1965; Simon, Thompson, and Smithburg [1950] 1991). Vigoda (2003) has claimed that most of the research studies on organizational politics have been perceived negatively while as (Drory, 2010) has mentioned that traditionally, it has been seen as evil.

Objective of the Study

To get the best candidate suitable for the job based on their capabilities.

To adopt the new methodology in the selection process assisting towards the modern business world.

Scope of the Study

The study can be applied in any institution having Human Resource, which occupies a significant place. This study is mainly made for the service sector, i.e., Educational Institution.

Research Methodology

The study is an Empirical Research conducted among the teaching faculty member of an Educational Institution. Details gathered through the means of Primary data collection via Google forms.

Sources of Data Collection Tools

Primary data collected through Google forms.

Secondary data used for review of literature includes the research publications which are enclosed in the references.

Sample Design of the Study

Sample size: 40 Faculty

Coverage of the study: the study is restricted to the Educational Sector.

Sampling technique: Probability sampling is where simple random sampling is used for collecting the data, where respondents are selected as per my wish and my convenience.

Techniques for Analysing Data

Data Analysis is done by using graphs and tables which are analyzed through Google forms.

Limitation of the Study

The result obtained is based on the data collected from the faculty members, and due to time lag, it is being enquired at the base level. The study does not support to disabled people, and we are trying our best to get to the adapted table to them.

Data Presentation from the Primary Data Collected (Findings)

Interpretation: Majority of the Sample belonging to the age group of 25-30 years.

Interpretation: Female occupies 55% of the total respondents.

Interpretation: out of the response collected, 42.5% of the respondents are working as an assistant professor.

Interpretation: out of the response collected 72.5% of the respondents entirely prefer Interview method for selection.

Interpretation: The survey projects that 57.5% of faculties opinion is positive about the direct interview process of the Institution and out of the remaining 35% of faculties have faced failure in an immediate interview, and 7.5% of the faculty give a neutral opinion.

Interpretation: As per the data collected, 27.5% of the respondents feel that favoritism and recommendation is the main reason for failure in a direct interview. And 22.5% of the respondents think that personal bias is also a part of the fault.

Interpretation: the survey represents, 50 % of the respondents strongly agree that a person’s real performance can’t be judged in 5 minutes of an interview.

Interpretation: the survey reveals that 37.5 % of the respondents strongly agree that a person’s physical characteristics affect the selection process, but 35% of the respondents are not in a position to judge.

Interpretation: this survey represents 82% of the respondents haven’t failed rejection due to natural look.

Interpretation: the survey represents, 40 % of the respondents agree that the interview method provides the best candidate.

Interpretation: As per the data collected, 32.5% of the respondents agree that fear is created during a direct interview. And 30% of the respondents disagree for the above. Approximately 5% of people feel that they don’t get fear or loss of confidence during the direct interview.

Interpretation: 40% of the data collected says that the duration available for the interview method is not sufficient for the selection of the best candidate.

Interpretation: From the above analysis, it is observed that 45% of the respondents agree that the interviewer will not listen carefully to what candidates say, and 40% strongly agree on the above lines.

Interpretation: the survey reveals that 40 % of the respondents agree that the performance of previously interviewed candidate affects the perception of the interviewer on further candidate. 35% of the respondents are not conscious about this question.

Interpretation: the survey reveals that 55 % of the respondents agree that the interviewer should rise questions on their respective specialized subject.

Interpretation: the survey reveals that majority of the respondents agree that the recommendation letter is essential during the interview and will affect the selection process.

Interpretation: 82.5% of the total respondents are aware of the Google forms.

Interpretation: the survey reveals that 37.5 % of the respondents agree that Google forms can be used in the method of interview. The positive aspect is that not even a single respondent say that strongly disagree on implementing Google forms in the interview process.

Suggestions

The Institution should follow new selection techniques towards hiring the best and suitable candidate.

Questions should be posed by the interviewer who is having expert knowledge in a different area of specialization.

Conclusion

From the above survey, it can be seen that majority of the people feel that interviewer will not listen to what the candidate is responding and due to favoritism and recommendation their chances of getting selected is less, and they agree towards changing the way of interview by using Google forms.

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